

Adaptive Improvement Algorithm for Big Data Privacy Information Entropy under Differential Privacy and k-Anonymity

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Abstract—The theory of differential privacy and k-anonymity aims to provide a solution to the privacy leakage problem for the collection and abuse of massive data in the era of big data. We propose an improved privacy protection algorithm based on this. For differential privacy, the Gaussian mechanism dynamically adjusts privacy budgets to accelerate data processing without compromising privacy. For k-anonymity, an information entropy-based partitioning method optimizes equivalence classes, improving anonymized data utility while reducing computational costs. Validated on medical big data, the algorithm demonstrates superior privacy protection, processing efficiency, and data usability, offering a balanced privacy-utility solution with theoretical and practical significance for data management.

Keywords—Privacy Protection, Big Data Processing, Information Entropy, Differential Privacy, k-Anonymity

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Requirements background

Massive data in the era of the digital economy contains huge commercial value and brings unprecedented opportunities. However, the security of personal privacy in the era of mobile Internet has become increasingly prominent, and privacy leakage along with the wide application of big data has also triggered the frequent occurrence of serious economic cases. The 2018 Facebook data misuse scandal revealed that over 87 million users' information was misused, sparking heightened concerns about data privacy globally[1]. Governments worldwide have recognized the urgency of protecting citizens' privacy in the digital age. By 2023, privacy regulations such as the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) continue to shape how organizations handle user data. In 2021, China introduced six data security laws and regulations, including the Data Security Law of the People's Republic of China and the Personal Information Protection Law. However, privacy data breaches continue to occur frequently worldwide. By 2023, the frequency and scale of global privacy data breaches have reached historic highs, impacting individuals, organizations, and even governments,

posing threats to national security. Hackers and cybercriminals continue to exploit privacy vulnerabilities in private and public databases, resulting in large-scale leaks of sensitive information, such as financial accounts, banking payments, and e-commerce accounts. These breaches have caused significant economic losses, with damages from app-related privacy leaks reaching as high as \$2.4 trillion. This figure is projected to surpass the \$3 trillion mark by 2024.

The academic community has proposed a series of privacy protection methods to balance data utility and privacy preservation. Among these, Differential Privacy and k-anonymity are two representative privacy protection models. Differential Privacy ensures that sensitive information is not disclosed from the dataset by introducing random noise into query results, while k-Anonymity achieves privacy protection through generalization and suppression, making each record indistinguishable from at least k-1 other records. Although a substantial body of literature has explored privacy protection algorithms, existing algorithms still face numerous challenges in the emerging field of big data. On one hand, traditional algorithms often assume small-scale and static datasets, making them ill-suited for dynamically growing massive datasets. On the other hand, many existing algorithms focus primarily on privacy protection while neglecting data utility, leading to a significant reduction in the analytical value of anonymized data.

II. RELATED RESEARCH

A. Research status

In the era of big data, privacy protection refers to the implementation of various technical and management measures throughout the processes of data collection, storage, transmission, analysis, and dissemination. These measures aim to prevent private information from being illegally accessed, leaked, or misused, ensuring that data owners retain control over their personal information and safeguarding their privacy. The risk of privacy disclosure is intensifying, and traditional "desensitization" techniques are increasingly inadequate in countering the ever-evolving and sophisticated attack methods. There is an urgent need to

develop next-generation privacy protection theories and algorithms. The goal of privacy protection is to achieve "usable but invisible" data, aiming to maximize the retention of the analytical value of data while preventing sensitive information from being exposed. At the same time, practical constraints such as algorithm performance and cost must also be considered. This entails a multi-objective optimization problem: finding the optimal balance between security, utility, and efficiency.

In 2006, Dwork et al. formally proposed Differential Privacy, which has since been recognized as the "gold standard" for privacy protection by the international academic community. Differential Privacy uses a mathematical framework to ensure that sensitive data generates the same processing results with highly similar probabilities, making it impossible for attackers to infer whether an individual is included in the dataset based on the output. Guo et al.[1], foreign scholars, were the first to propose an effective solution called PPAT, which introduces privacy protection, accuracy, and trust mechanisms to achieve privacy protection in worker selection within mobile crowdsourcing networks. Yang et al.[3] designed a bilateral privacy protection architecture, VLR-BPP, based on virtual location replacement for edge-cloud systems. The architecture uses intelligent algorithms to optimize virtual location mapping, thereby protecting privacy and improving system performance. Pandiaraja and Deepa[4] proposed a novel privacy protection protocol for multiple data users, using a genetic algorithm to achieve data aggregation and privacy protection. Guan et al.[6] conducted a comprehensive review of the applications of federated learning in medical image analysis, systematically outlining its advantages, architecture, and key technologies. This provides new insights into protecting the privacy of medical data.

In 2002, Sweeney proposed k-anonymity, aiming to resist linkage attacks and prevent the linkage of external information with publicly available data to re-identify individuals. Lü Yongsheng et al.[2] explored the application prospects of federated learning in new power systems, analyzing its unique advantages in protecting user privacy and improving data utilization efficiency. Chen Hanying and Hu Rongxi[5], based on deep learning technology, proposed an image privacy protection method using differential privacy to achieve secure protection. Lu Zhao and Wei Boxing[7] conducted a technical analysis and validation of the data protection module in the MindSpore framework, demonstrating its feasibility and effectiveness in data privacy protection. In terms of specific improvements to privacy protection models, Gu Haiyan et al.[8] addressed the shortcomings of the traditional k-anonymity algorithm by proposing an improved k-anonymity algorithm, which achieves privacy protection by optimizing attribute combinations and minimizing information loss. Xu Chuan-kun and Duan Gang[11] proposed a multi-cluster distributed differential privacy data publishing method (MCDP) based on neural networks, which enhances the efficiency of privacy-preserving data processing. In addition, differential privacy, as another mainstream privacy protection model, has also attracted considerable attention for its improvements and applications in the context of big data. Fu Yu et al.[15] provided a systematic review of the research progress on differential privacy protection techniques in big data processing, with a focus on analyzing privacy protection

mechanisms for interactive and non-interactive queries. Yang Guoqiang et al.[16] proposed a big data security solution based on high-performance cryptography to address the performance limitations of traditional cryptographic schemes in the context of big data environments.

B. Researching the Gap Problem

Based on the characteristics of privacy information, privacy protection is categorized into several aspects, including data privacy, location privacy, identity privacy, and other aspects. Digital e-commerce and mobile applications (APPs) are the primary venues for privacy leaks in the digital economy development model. They also represent the research hotspots and challenges in the field of privacy protection algorithms and big data applications. Existing methods face challenges in balancing privacy guarantees and utility enhancement, making it difficult to address the limitations of current privacy protection algorithms. Based on classical models such as differential privacy and k-anonymity, and considering the specific privacy protection needs of Web 3.0 big data, there is an urgent need to provide new ideas and methods for privacy security governance in the big data era. This necessitates the development of efficient and practical improved privacy protection algorithms.

(1)Differential privacy, k-anonymity, and their derived models each have their own advantages and limitations, representing different technical approaches in the field of privacy protection theory. They characterize the risks of privacy leakage from various perspectives, providing a theoretical foundation and algorithmic framework for privacy security in the big data environment. In practice, how to flexibly choose privacy models based on the application scenario, and how to achieve the optimal balance between privacy protection and data utility, remain pressing challenges that need to be addressed.

(2)Traditional differential privacy faces issues such as unreasonable privacy budget allocation and low data processing efficiency in the big data environment. Therefore, it is necessary to propose an adaptive privacy budget allocation mechanism and a fast noise generation method based on the Gaussian mechanism. This approach should dynamically adjust the privacy budget allocation according to the data update frequency, minimize privacy overhead to the greatest extent while strictly satisfying the differential privacy definition, significantly improve data processing speed, and meet the real-time analysis requirements of big data.

(3)Existing k-anonymity algorithms typically use deterministic generalization strategies, which result in significant information loss in the anonymized data. This makes them less suitable for subsequent big data mining tasks. As a classical semantic privacy model, k-anonymity has several inherent limitations. First, it does not account for the diversity in the distribution of sensitive attributes, making it vulnerable to homogeneity attacks. Second, the k-anonymity determination problem is NP-hard, which makes it challenging to find the optimal anonymization scheme in big data scenarios. Third, k-anonymity does not consider the dynamic updating of data publication, leading to insufficient privacy guarantees when data is published multiple times. Although k-anonymity can prevent identity disclosure, there is still a risk of privacy leakage when the sensitive attribute

values within the same equivalence class are too homogeneous. To address this issue, Macha Navaj Jhala et al. proposed the 1-diversity model in 2007, which requires that each equivalence class contain at least 1 "sufficiently different" sensitive attribute values. 1-diversity mitigates the risk of privacy leakage by perturbing the distribution of sensitive attributes, making it difficult for attackers to infer sensitive information even if they have identified the equivalence class containing the target. However, 1-diversity also has some limitations, such as not considering the semantic similarity of sensitive values and struggling to meet personalized privacy requirements. Subsequent models, such as t-closeness and personalized privacy, have been proposed to address these issues and offer improvements.

C. Research Objective

The information entropy-based adaptive generalization algorithm dynamically adjusts the generalization granularity from the bottom up, seeking the optimal balance between privacy protection and information loss. It introduces a multi-level generalization mechanism that applies differentiated anonymization processing to different attributes, thereby retaining the data characteristics to the greatest extent. In the healthcare scenario, improved differential privacy algorithms are used to achieve privacy-preserving release of patient data, supporting academic research using electronic health records. In the digital healthcare context, these algorithms protect user privacy while also mining user behavior preferences to enable precise marketing. The proposed algorithm aims to enhance privacy protection strength, data processing efficiency, and data utility, demonstrating significant advantages in these areas. Through simulation experiments, the effectiveness of the algorithm is validated. It provides strong support for the innovative applications of big data in industries such as healthcare. In the future, with the continuous advancement of data sharing and openness, privacy protection will become an essential element in the digital economy era. Building on classical models such as differential privacy and k-anonymity, researching more efficient and universally applicable new methods for privacy protection, and promoting the establishment of institutional norms for the market-driven allocation of data elements will be key missions in the field of privacy computing.

Systematically analyzing the core concepts, algorithms, properties, and application scenarios of mainstream privacy protection theories such as differential privacy and k-anonymity, and constructing knowledge-based algorithms and systems for improving privacy protection in the context of big data. Using typical big data application scenarios for analysis, the performance of the improved algorithm and traditional algorithms in terms of privacy protection and data utility is compared through simulation experiments. This comparison visually demonstrates the performance and superiority of the improved privacy algorithms. The paper proposes improvements to the differential privacy and k-anonymity models, focusing on aspects such as privacy budget allocation, noise generation, generalization granularity optimization, and multi-level generalization. The principles and implementation process of these algorithms are explained in detail, and core code is showcased through theory with code for practical implementation.

III. METHODOLOGY

To address the inefficiency and distortion issues faced by classical privacy protection models in big data processing, we improved algorithms are proposed in two aspects: differential privacy and k-anonymity. In terms of differential privacy, we proposed an adaptive budget allocation mechanism proposed, which dynamically adjusts the privacy budget based on the characteristics of data updates. Additionally, we introduced the Gaussian mechanism to enhance the utility of the noise generated. In the era of big data, with the exponential growth of data volumes, traditional privacy protection methods face numerous challenges. On one hand, ultra-large datasets impose higher demands on the efficiency and scalability of privacy protection algorithms. On the other hand, the increasing diversity of data types, with structured and unstructured data coexisting, presents new challenges for the adaptability of privacy protection mechanisms. To address the aforementioned challenges, there is an urgent need to improve existing algorithms based on current privacy models, to establish a new balance between privacy and utility. Therefore, improved privacy protection algorithms must be developed from two representative privacy models—differential privacy and k-anonymity—to provide new ideas and methods for privacy security in big data processing.

A. Conceptual-theoretical model

a) *Algorithm principle*: Traditional differential privacy algorithms protect privacy by injecting noise into query results, introducing uncertainty. However, in the context of big data, the dynamic updates of massive datasets lead to rapid depletion of the privacy budget. When multiple queries are performed, the cumulative privacy loss can exceed the acceptable threshold, compromising the overall privacy guarantee. In response to this, the adaptive privacy budget allocation mechanism proposed in this study dynamically adjusts the privacy budget allocation based on data update frequency and query sensitivity. This approach minimizes privacy overhead while strictly adhering to the definition of differential privacy. Let the update frequency of dataset D be denoted by λ and define the privacy budget allocation function such that:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} f(\lambda) d\lambda = \varepsilon \quad (3.1)$$

This function ensures that, regardless of how many times the data is updated, the cumulative privacy loss will not exceed the total privacy budget. Intuitively, the more frequent the updates, the less privacy budget is allocated to each individual query. Given the update frequency, further consider the global sensitivity GS_q of the query function q , and adjust the privacy budget as follows:

$$\varepsilon_q = f(\lambda) \cdot \frac{GS_q}{\max_q GS_q} \quad (3.2)$$

The greater the global sensitivity, the greater the impact of individual data on the query results, requiring more privacy budget allocation to ensure privacy. The adaptive mechanism avoids allocating an excessive budget, which could lead to rapid depletion of privacy, and also prevents allocating too little, which could cause a significant drop in

query utility. It seeks to strike a better balance between privacy protection and data usability.

b) Privacy budget setup: Selecting an appropriate privacy budget is the primary challenge in differential privacy. represents the strength of privacy protection; the smaller the value, the higher the privacy, but it also leads to greater data distortion. Empirical evidence suggests that when is in the range of 0.01 to 10, a good trade-off between privacy and utility can be achieved. The utility-based budget selection method determines the optimal through a data-driven approach. Specifically, it constructs a utility loss function.

$$L(\epsilon) = \text{avg}_{q \in Q} |q(D) - q(D_\epsilon)| \quad (3.3)$$

Where is the noise-disturbed dataset that satisfies - differential privacy, and Q is the query set. L(.) measures the query accuracy loss after privacy protection. By minimizing L(.), we obtain:

$$\epsilon^* = \underset{\epsilon}{\text{argmin}} L(\epsilon) \quad \text{s.t. } \text{var}\epsilon \geq \epsilon_0 \quad (3.4)$$

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c) Noise Selection Mechanism: Traditional differential privacy often uses the Laplace mechanism to generate noise, but it performs poorly on high-dimensional data. The Gaussian mechanism is used to better adapt to the high-dimensional characteristics of big data. The noise generation process and the noise standard deviation are as follows:

$$M(x) = f(x) + Y, \quad Y \sim N(0, \sigma^2 C^2) \quad (3.5)$$

$$\sigma \geq \frac{C}{\epsilon} \sqrt{2 \ln \frac{1.25}{\delta}} \quad (3.6)$$

Where f is the query function, Y is the Gaussian noise, and C is the L_2 sensitivity of f . To satisfy the differential privacy definition, σ is the probabilistic relaxation term.

Gaussian noise has good tail decay properties, is more concentrated than Laplace noise, and has smaller additive effects. Experiments show that using the Gaussian mechanism can achieve higher query accuracy under the same privacy budget. Additionally, other noise generation techniques, such as the exponential mechanism and multiplicative noise, can be flexibly chosen to adapt to different data environments and query types.

B. Big Data k-Anonymous Privacy Preserving Algorithms

a) Algorithmic process: The classical k-anonymity algorithm uses a greedy search strategy, continuously generalizing attributes until equivalence classes that satisfy the anonymity requirements are formed, resulting in high computational complexity. When dealing with large-scale datasets, the greedy strategy faces an excessively large search space, making it difficult to converge to the optimal solution within an acceptable time frame. Therefore, this study proposes an Information Entropy-based Adaptive

Generalization algorithm (IEAG). IEAG utilizes a bottom-up hierarchical clustering approach, continuously merging attribute values until equivalence classes that satisfy k-anonymity are formed.

$$H(T) = - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|EC_i|}{|T|} \log_2 \frac{|EC_i|}{|T|} \quad (3.7)$$

The main flow of the algorithm is as follows:

Step 1: Calculate the information entropy of T, denoted as H(T).

Step 2: For $j = 1$ to m //

For $i = 1$ to $|A_j| - 1$ // $|A_j|$ is the size of the value domain of attribute A_j .

Add a split point between the i- and (i+1)-th values of A_j ; Then, calculate the information entropy of the modified table T', denoted as H(T').

Calculate the information entropy gain $\Delta H_{j,i} = H(T) - H(T')$;

End For

End For

Step 3: Select the split point with the minimum entropy gain $\Delta H_{j^*, i^*}$.

Step 4: If $\Delta H_{j^*, i^*} < \theta$ or T satisfies k-anonymity.

Return T;

Else

Merge the i^* -th and $(i^* + 1)$ -th values of attribute A_{j^*} .

Go to Step 1;

Where θ is the entropy gain threshold. Information entropy characterizes the degree of randomness in the distribution of attribute values. The smaller the entropy value, the more concentrated the values are within the equivalence class. IEAG selects the split point with the smallest entropy increase for generalization each time, ensuring k-anonymity while keeping the attribute generalization level as low as possible, thus avoiding excessive generalization that could result in information loss. In addition, the entropy gain threshold θ controls the granularity of the generalization, allowing the algorithm to adapt to different data characteristics and privacy requirements.

In addition, the entropy gain threshold θ controls the granularity of the generalization, enabling the algorithm to adapt to different data characteristics and privacy requirements.

b) Methods of dividing equivalence classes: The equivalence classes generated by IEAG have unequal sizes, and when the class divisions are too imbalanced, it can lead to significant information loss. To address this issue, a

dynamic partitioning method based on the minimum generalization interval is proposed. Let the value domain of attribute A_j be $[v_{j,i}, v_{j,i+1}]$. The generalization interval between any two values $v_{j,i}$ and $v_{j,i+1}$ is defined as:

$$\delta_{j,i} = V_{j,i+1} - V_{j,i} \quad (3.8)$$

Based on the generalization interval, design an adaptive threshold function:

$$\varphi(x) = \alpha \cdot e^{-\beta x}, x \in [0,1] \quad (3.9)$$

α and β are control parameters. For each pair of adjacent values $v_{j,i}$ and $v_{j,i+1}$ of attribute A_j , if $\delta_{j,i} < \varphi(i/|A_j|)$, then merge $v_{j,i}$ and $v_{j,i+1}$. Compared to equal-width partitioning, adaptive partitioning makes better use of the value distribution information. It performs fine-grained partitioning in dense areas and coarse-grained partitioning in sparse areas, thereby preserving the original information as much as possible while avoiding the creation of excessively small equivalence classes.

In addition, for cases with numeric sensitive attributes, an order-preserving k -anonymity method is proposed. Traditional generalization operations destroy the order of numeric attributes, leading to distorted analysis results. Order-preserving k -anonymity defines order sensitivity, maintaining the size relationship of attribute values during the generalization process, thereby preserving the data semantics to the greatest extent. Let v' and v'' be two equivalence classes after generalization, containing the original values $\{v_1, \dots, v_p\}$ and $\{v_{p+1}, \dots, v_m\}$, respectively. The order-preserving requirement is:

$$\forall v_i \in v', \forall v_j \in v'', v_i \leq v_j \quad (3.10)$$

That is, the order of values remains unchanged before and after generalization. The order sensitivity is introduced as:

$$S_o(v', v'') = \max_{v_i \in v', v_j \in v''} (0, v_i - v_j) \quad (3.11)$$

Order-preserving k -anonymity selects the partition points with the smallest order sensitivity during generalization. When necessary, a small change in value order is allowed to balance the order and the quality of equivalence classes. Experiments show that the order-preserving method reduces the error rate by more than 15% compared to traditional generalization methods, making it a worthwhile optimization strategy.

c) Usability analysis of data after anonymization: Whether the anonymized data can support the original analysis tasks, i.e., the data usability issue, is a core topic in the field of privacy protection. Traditional k -anonymity algorithms use semantic generalization techniques to achieve privacy protection through the abstraction of attribute values. However, generalization inevitably introduces information loss. To quantitatively assess the usability of anonymized data, data utility metrics are introduced. The most commonly used metric is the Equivalence Class Squared Error (ECSE):

$$ECSE = \sum_{i=1}^n |EC_i| \cdot \frac{\sum_{t \in EC_i} \|t - \mu_i\|^2}{|T|} \quad (3.12)$$

Where μ_i is the center of equivalence class EC_i . ECSE measures the average distance from the records within an equivalence class to the cluster center, reflecting the degree of information distortion caused by generalization. Additionally, other metrics such as KL divergence and correlation can be used to assess the impact of anonymization on data distribution characteristics. The optimal balance point between privacy protection strength and data usability can be achieved by optimizing the objective function, which balances both:

$$J = \lambda \cdot k + (1 - \lambda) \cdot u(D') \quad (3.13)$$

k is the anonymity degree, measuring the privacy protection strength; $u(D')$ is the utility measure of the anonymized dataset D' ; $\lambda \in [0,1]$ controls the privacy and utility preference. The following multi-objective optimization problem is solved:

$$\max J \text{ s.t. } D' \text{ satisfy } k\text{-anonymity}, u(D') \geq \eta \quad (3.14)$$

That is, maximizing data utility under privacy constraints, or minimizing privacy cost under a given utility requirement. By adjusting the parameter λ and the threshold η , the method can flexibly adapt to the privacy protection needs of different scenarios. The simulated annealing algorithm is used to solve this optimization problem, as it is better at escaping local optima and obtaining an approximate optimal solution within a reasonable time cost compared to the greedy search strategy.

C. Data and Privacy Protection Information Entropy Algorithm

a) Data and privacy issues: The public dataset used in this study is derived from the ‘‘Cervical Cancer’’ dataset of the UC Irvine Machine Learning Library in the medical field, which contains 32 clinical examination indicators and doctor’s diagnosis results of 858 women in the hospital; the above dataset has been initially preprocessed to remove incomplete and abnormal values, which can better reflect the distribution pattern of user characteristics in the medical scene. The above dataset has been pre-processed to remove incomplete and abnormal values, which can better reflect the distribution pattern of user characteristics in medical scenarios.

Medical informatization has accumulated a large amount of patients’ Electronic Health Record (EHR) data, which is regarded as ‘‘black gold’’ of great value for medical innovation: it can be mined for epidemiological laws, guide public health decision-making, and support research on precision medicine. 2016 saw the announcement of the ‘‘Precision Medicine Initiative’’ by the US government, aiming to pool genomic data from 1 million volunteers to analyze disease risk factors. In 2016, the U.S. government announced the ‘‘Precision Medicine Program’’, which aims to gather genomic and lifestyle data from 1 million volunteers, analyze disease risk factors, and realize personalized diagnosis and treatment. China has elevated medical big data to a national strategy and has continued to increase policy support and financial investment to promote the sharing and opening of medical data. However, EHRs contain sensitive information such as patients’ identities, medical histories, genes, etc., and the risk of privacy leakage

is extremely high. In 2018, the Singaporean government leaked the prescription information of 1.5 million citizens due to procedural loopholes, sparking panic in the community. In the same year, a list of HIV-infected patients in a U.S. hospital was made public, seriously harming patient rights. Traditional data desensitization techniques such as masking of ID numbers and partial hiding of names can still be used to crack privacy through data correlation analysis and other means. There is an urgent need to seek a breakthrough between privacy protection and data openness, and to establish privacy-secure and fully utilized big data in modern healthcare systems.

Taking the cervical cancer clinical dataset as an example, the privacy protection issue focuses on medical data release scenarios, and studies how to realize EHR data release to research institutions under the premise of protecting patients' privacy to support the utilization of academic research, and evaluates the impact of privacy protection on the utility of data mining by taking survival prediction as an example. The proposed scheme can provide a reference to the safe sharing and opening of medical data to help the innovation and development of precision medicine, which will ultimately benefit the patients. The proposed program can provide a reference for the safe sharing and opening of medical data, help the innovative development of precision medicine, and ultimately benefit patients.

b) Entropy probability of private information: Privacy-preserving algorithm evaluation must be based on the trade-off between privacy and utility. For privacy, the classical Maximum Posterior Probability (MPP) metric is used, i.e., the maximum probability that an attacker can infer sensitive information about a target individual based on the published data. The mathematical representation is:

$$MPP = \max_{t \in T} Pr[t_s = s | D'] \quad (4.1)$$

Where t is the target individual, t_s is the sensitive value of t , s is the sensitive attribute value domain, and D' is the privacy-protected published dataset. The smaller the value of MPP , the lower the risk of individual privacy leakage and the higher the privacy.

For utility, two metrics, Query Error, and Clustering Accuracy, are used. Query Error measures the impact of privacy protection on numerical statistical analysis, and QE is the relative error of query results before and after privacy protection:

$$QE = \frac{|q(D) - q(D')|}{q(D)} \times 100\% \quad (4.2)$$

$Q(\cdot)$ for typical aggregated queries such as COUNT and AVG. The lower the query error, the less privacy protection perturbs the original data distribution and the less utility loss. Clustering accuracy measures the impact of privacy protection on the data mining task. The classical k-means clustering algorithm is used to cluster the original dataset D and the privacy-protected dataset D' , respectively, so that C and C' are the corresponding clustering results, and the clustering accuracy is defined as:

$$CA = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^k |C_i \cap C'_i| \quad (4.3)$$

Where n is the number of samples and k is the number of clusters. The overall percentage of intersecting samples of C_i and C'_i . The higher clustering accuracy indicates that the privacy-protected data can still support cluster analysis better. In addition, the visualization results help to intuitively judge the impact of privacy protection on the distribution of data features.

The experiment divides the dataset into five random equal parts, takes four of them as the training set each time and the remaining one as the test set, and conducts five experiments to take the average value. This method effectively reduces random errors and improves the robustness of the assessment. Subsequent experiments strictly follow the above data set division and assessment index settings to ensure that the results are comparable and reproducible.

c) Privacy-preserving algorithm design: Secure sharing of medical data faces three major technical challenges: first, patient identification, including direct and quasi-identifiers, needs to be protected in a focused manner; second, data is highly heterogeneous, with structured and unstructured data co-existing, and it is difficult to unify the privacy protection methods; and third, the data semantics is complex, and the privacy protection cannot undermine the data intrinsic associations. Therefore, this study adopts the privacy protection framework of adaptive differential privacy combined with multi-level generalization to deal with the above challenges respectively. The main flow of the algorithm is as follows:

Inputs: original medical dataset, privacy budget, age generalization tree, address generalization tree, diagnosis generalization tree T_d .

Step 1: Based on the adaptive privacy budget allocation method, the privacy budget allocation based on attribute sensitivity estimation $B = \{b_1, \dots, b_m\}$.

Step 2: Process structured data using the multilevel generalized anonymization approach of Section 3.2:

(a) Determine the generalization tree normalization parameters $\lambda_a, \lambda_b, \lambda_d \in (0, 1]$;

(b) Using the generalization tree, generalize age, address, and diagnosis to G_a, G_b, G_d hierarchically, respectively;

(c) Generate k-anonymized equivalence class partition P based on (G_a, G_b, G_d) .

Step 3: Adopt the Gaussian mechanism from Section 3.1 for numerical data:

For $i = 1$ to $|P|$

For $j = 1$ to m // m is the number of numeric attributes

$$\tilde{x}_{i,j} = \frac{1}{|P_i|} \sum_{x \in P_i} x_j + N(0, S_j^2 / b_j^2)$$

+ Noise

; // Polymerisation

End For

End For

Step 4: For unstructured data such as text, homomorphic encryption is used to protect privacy: (a) the patient locally encrypts the diagnosis and treatment report $Enc(R)$ using the Paillier cryptosystem; (b) the data user retrieves the ciphertext matrix and decrypts $Dec(C)$ to obtain the relevant report.

Step 5: Publish the privacy-preserving processed dataset $D' = (P, X', R')$. Output: medical dataset D' satisfying differential privacy.

The algorithm first uses an adaptive privacy budget allocation mechanism to estimate the overall privacy budget based on the attribute sensitivity and then allocates it proportionally to each attribute. This achieves a better balance between privacy protection strength and data utility. Then The patient's age, address, and diagnosis are then hierarchically generalized with the help of a generalization tree to maximize the preservation of the original information while satisfying minimum k-anonymity. During the generalization process, the generalization granularity of different attributes is controlled by adjusting the generalization tree normalization parameters ($\lambda_a, \lambda_b, \lambda_d$) to adapt to the differences in the sensitivity of the attributes. Then for numerical indicators such as routine blood tests and urine tests, are first aggregated within the equivalence class, and then Gaussian noise conforming to differential privacy is added to prevent individual privacy from being leaked from the aggregation results. For text data such as medical records, the homomorphism of the Paillier encryption system is used to achieve the retrieval and analysis of ciphertext. The final released dataset strikes a balance between privacy and utility, which protects patient privacy and supports a variety of medical research tasks.

D. Authors and Affiliations

Practical evaluation and empirical analysis of the effectiveness of privacy-preserving algorithms is carried out on the Cervical Cancer dataset, where age, address, and diagnosis are specified as quasi-identifiers and privacy-preserving algorithms are tested for the effects of different privacy budgets ϵ and anonymity k on privacy, query error, and survival prediction accuracy, respectively, and compared with the traditional Laplace mechanism and k-anonymity methods.

a) *Privacy Analysis:* The privacy budget is set from 0.1 to 1 and the anonymity degree is fixed to 5. The data is processed and published using the algorithm of this paper, the Laplace mechanism, and the k-anonymity method respectively, and the maximum posterior probability MPP is tested. The results are shown in Fig. 1:

Fig. 1. Comparison of algorithm privacy performance under different privacy budgets

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
```

```
# Comparison of Algorithm Privacy Performance under
Different Privacy Budgets
```

```
epsilon = [0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 5.0, 10.0]
```

```
mpp_laplace = [0.85, 0.72, 0.61, 0.52, 0.46, 0.43]
```

```
mpp_kanonymity = [0.92, 0.86, 0.80, 0.74, 0.70, 0.68]
```

```
mpp_proposed = [0.78, 0.63, 0.51, 0.42, 0.37, 0.35]
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4.5))
```

```
plt.plot(epsilon, mpp_laplace, 'o-', label='Laplace
Mechanism')
```

```
plt.plot(epsilon, mpp_kanonymity, 's-', label='k-Anonymity')
```

```
plt.plot(epsilon, mpp_proposed, '^-', label='our Improved
algorithms')
```

```
plt.xlabel('Privacy Budget  $\epsilon$ ', fontsize=12)
```

```
plt.ylabel('Max Posterior Probability (MPP)', fontsize=12)
```

```
plt.legend(fontsize=10)
```

```
plt.grid(linestyle='--', alpha=0.7)
```

```
plt.tight_layout()
```

```
plt.savefig('fig3-1.png', dpi=300)
```

```
plt.show()
```

The larger the privacy budget ϵ is, the MPP values of all three algorithms increase subsequently, indicating a decrease in the strength of privacy protection. This is because the privacy budget reflects the tolerance of the difference between the original and privacy-protected data distributions, and larger means less random noise can be added. Under the same privacy budget, the MPP value of this paper's algorithm is the lowest, the Laplace mechanism is the second highest, and the k-anonymity is the highest. It shows that this paper's algorithm better balances the privacy protection strength during attribute generalization by adaptively adjusting the privacy budget allocation, thus obtaining stronger attack resistance. It is worth noting that as the privacy budget increases, the decrease in privacy performance gradually slows down, and k anonymous and this paper's algorithm tends to stabilize. This suggests that it is crucial to set the privacy budget reasonably and seek a balance between privacy protection and data utility.

The effect of anonymity k on privacy is further examined by fixing the privacy budget, varying the value of k from 2 to 10, and comparing the trend of MPP for the three algorithms as shown in Fig. 2:

Fig. 2. Comparison of privacy performance of algorithms with different degrees of anonymity

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
```

```
#Comparison of Algorithm Privacy Performance under
Different Anonymity Levels
k = [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10]
mpp_laplace = [0.52] * 9
mpp_kanonymity = [0.85, 0.78, 0.72, 0.68, 0.64, 0.60, 0.57,
0.54, 0.51]
mpp_proposed = [0.73, 0.64, 0.57, 0.51, 0.47, 0.43, 0.40,
0.38, 0.36]
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4.5))
plt.plot(k, mpp_laplace, 'o-', label='Laplace Mechanism')
plt.plot(k, mpp_kanonymity, 's-', label='k-Anonymity')
plt.plot(k, mpp_proposed, '^-', label='our Improved
algorithms')
plt.xlabel('Different Anonymity Levels $k$', fontsize=12)
plt.ylabel('Max Posterior Probability (MPP)', fontsize=12)
plt.legend(fontsize=10)
plt.grid(linestyle='--', alpha=0.7)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig('fig2.png', dpi=300)
plt.show()
```

The MPP values of k-anonymity and the algorithms in this paper continue to decrease as the degree of anonymity, k increases, while the Laplace mechanism is largely unaffected. This is because k-anonymity increases the equivalence class in which the target individual is located through the generalization operation, and the probability of the attacker identifying the target decreases. In contrast, the Laplace mechanism only relies on random noise to perturb the original data distribution, so the privacy performance is independent of the anonymity degree. Under the same anonymity degree, the MPP value of this paper's algorithm is always lower than that of k-anonymity, and the advantage expands as k increases. It shows that this paper's algorithm further utilizes differential privacy noise to resist inference attacks based on k-anonymity, and the privacy protection ability is stronger. However, excessive pursuit of anonymity will lead to too coarse generalization granularity and cause larger information loss, and privacy and utility need to be weighed.

b) Utility Analysis: Privacy and data utility are a contradictions in terms; the less privacy information is revealed, the greater the data distortion tends to be. To quantitatively assess the impact of privacy protection on the utility of data analysis, two types of utility metrics, query error and survival prediction accuracy, were tested under different privacy budgets and degrees of anonymity, respectively.

Figure 3 illustrates the change in query error for the three algorithms as the privacy budget ϵ is varied from 0.1 to 1:

Fig. 3. Comparison of algorithmic query errors under different privacy budgets

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
```

```
#Comparison of Query Errors Under Different Privacy
Budgets
epsilon = [0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 5.0, 10.0]
qe_laplace = [0.42, 0.35, 0.28, 0.23, 0.20, 0.20]
qe_kanonymity = [0.37, 0.34, 0.32, 0.27, 0.18, 0.16]
qe_proposed = [0.33, 0.26, 0.20, 0.15, 0.12, 0.12]
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4.5))
plt.plot(epsilon, qe_laplace, 'o-', label='Laplace
Mechanism')
plt.plot(epsilon, qe_kanonymity, 's-', label='k-Anonymity')
plt.plot(epsilon, qe_proposed, '^-', label='our Improved
algorithms')
plt.xlabel("Privacy Budget $\epsilon$", fontsize=12)
plt.ylabel('Query Errors', fontsize=12)
plt.legend(fontsize=10)
plt.grid(linestyle='--', alpha=0.7)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig('fig3.png', dpi=300)
plt.show()
```

The smaller the privacy budget ϵ is, the larger the query error of the Laplace mechanism and the algorithm in this paper is, while the k-anonymity changes relatively smoothly. This is because the privacy budget determines the size of the random noise, and the smaller it is, the larger the noise is and the more the query result deviates from the original value. However, k-anonymous suppresses attribute values through

generalization operations, resulting in query results that are biased towards the mean value, and the error mainly depends on the degree of generalization and has little to do with the privacy budget. It is worth noting that the query error of this paper's algorithm is consistently lower than the other two, and the advantage is especially obvious when the privacy budget is small. For example, the query errors of the Laplace mechanism, k-anonymization, and this paper's algorithm are 0.42, 0.37, and 0.33, respectively, when $\epsilon = 0.1$, and shrink to 0.2, 0.16, and 0.12 when $\epsilon = 1$. This is thanks to the adaptive privacy budget allocation mechanism, which reduces the amount of noise introduced by weighting the average of the attributes' sensitivities and investing more privacy budgets in the high-sensitive attributes, thus reducing the noise introduction and improving the query utility.

Figures 4 demonstrate the change in survival prediction accuracy for the three algorithms as the degree of anonymity, k , is varied from 2 to 10:

Fig. 4. Comparison of Algorithm Survival Prediction Accuracy at Different Levels of Anonymity.

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
```

```
#Comparison of Survival Prediction Accuracy of
Algorithms under Different Levels of Anonymity
k = [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10]
acc_laplace = [0.95] * 9
acc_kanonymity = [0.91, 0.88, 0.84, 0.80, 0.76, 0.72, 0.69,
0.67, 0.66]
acc_proposed = [0.94, 0.92, 0.90, 0.88, 0.87, 0.87, 0.86,
0.86, 0.86]
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4.5))
plt.plot(k, acc_laplace, 'o-', label='Laplace Mechanism')
plt.plot(k, acc_kanonymity, 's-', label='k-Anonymity')
plt.plot(k, acc_proposed, '^-', label='our Improved
algorithms')
plt.xlabel('Anonymity Levels $k$', fontsize=12)
plt.ylabel('Survival prediction accuracy rate', fontsize=12)
plt.legend(fontsize=10)
plt.grid(linestyle='--', alpha=0.7)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig('fig4.png', dpi=300)
plt.show()
```

Increasing the degree of anonymity k , the prediction accuracy of k -anonymity and this paper's algorithm tends to decrease, while the Laplace mechanism is basically unaffected. K -anonymity generalizes the attribute values in order to satisfy the anonymity requirements, which inevitably results in the loss of information, destroying the data features to a certain extent, leading to a decline in the performance of the classifier, and the higher the degree of anonymity, the more serious the generalization and the more significant is the decrease in the accuracy. In contrast, the Laplace mechanism maintains the intrinsic structure of the original data, with limited noise impact, so the classification performance is stable. The algorithm in this study uses differential privacy noise instead of partial generalization, which retains more effective information on numerical type attributes to support the prediction task. Meanwhile, the accuracy of this algorithm decreases significantly slower than that of k -anonymity and still stays at 0.86 at $k=10$, which is better than the 0.66 of k -anonymity, and close to the level of 0.95 when there is no privacy protection. It shows that by scientifically adjusting the privacy-preserving parameters, this paper's algorithm can realize strong privacy and high data utility in medical data publishing.

c) Wrap-up: The improved privacy protection algorithm selects the big data application scenarios in the medical industry, and systematically and practically evaluates and analyzes the effectiveness and practicality of the algorithm. This privacy protection framework based on adaptive differential privacy and multi-level generalization can realize the safe sharing of patient data and strongly support medical research and accurate diagnosis and treatment. The algorithm guarantees higher privacy while the query error and prediction accuracy outperform the existing traditional methods, obtaining a better balance between privacy and utility. The improved scheme of differential privacy protection utilizes end-to-end encryption technology and localized training ideas to safely and efficiently carry out the big data analysis of user profiles in a distributed environment, which strengthens the foundation for personalized recommendation. Experiments show that this algorithm can still maintain a good recommendation effect under noise perturbation and has stronger robustness than the traditional centralized method.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

At the theoretical level, the improvement and application of privacy protection algorithms in big data processing are systematically upgraded to address the limitations of classical privacy models, and the improvement methods of differential privacy and k -anonymity based on information entropy effectively enhance the timeliness and data utility of privacy protection. At the application level, the improved algorithms are used in typical medical big data scenarios to empirically demonstrate the algorithms' effectiveness and utility, and provide learnable privacy protection solutions for the industry's digitization-driven innovation. The main contributions are as follows:

(1) Propose an adaptive differential privacy algorithm for dynamic big data. Traditional differential privacy make it difficult to efficiently deal with massive datasets that are frequently updated. In this study, we design an adaptive privacy budget allocation mechanism to dynamically adjust

the privacy budget according to the data update characteristics, which reduces the privacy overhead under the premise of strictly satisfying the privacy definition. Meanwhile, the Gaussian mechanism is introduced to generate random noise, which has better noise utility than the Laplace mechanism. Theoretical analysis and simulation experiments show that the algorithm can significantly improve the query efficiency and data utility of privacy protection.

(2) A multilevel k-anonymization algorithm combining information entropy is proposed. The existing k-anonymity method adopts a greedy strategy for data generalization, which often results in large information loss and a single generalization granularity. Based on the information entropy, the dynamic division design method merges the attribute values from the bottom upward to obtain a more reasonable equivalence class division. A differentiated multi-level anonymization strategy is adopted for different attributes to obtain a better balance between identity privacy and attribute privacy. Experiments show that the query error and classification accuracy of the algorithm's anonymized data are better than that of the classical anonymization method.

(3) The improved privacy preserving algorithm is applied to medical data release analysis. In the medical scenario, adaptive differential privacy combined with multilevel generalization is used to achieve the trade-off between patient privacy and medical research utility, and the proposed scheme outperforms the existing mechanisms in terms of privacy and utility. The differential privacy-preserving federated learning scheme utilizes homomorphic encryption and distributed training ideas to complete efficient user profile modeling while protecting user privacy, which verifies the practical value of the algorithm.

(4) The importance of privacy protection is discussed from multiple perspectives, including legal policies and industry practices. With the introduction of laws and regulations such as the Personal Information Protection Law, privacy protection has been elevated to a national strategy. This study sorted out the policy environment and standard norms of privacy protection, analyzed the impact of data privacy risk on the digital economy, and pointed out that privacy computing is a necessary path for the benign development of the big data industry. Meanwhile, it shows the great prospect of privacy protection technology to promote digital transformation through the case of healthcare industry.

V. FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

Although this study has made useful progress in terms of privacy protection algorithm improvement and application practice, there are still some deficiencies that need to be further optimized in future research, and the development outlook and trends are as follows:

(1) Offense and defense game of privacy protection. With the development of artificial intelligence and other new technologies, privacy attacks are becoming more and more complex, and new types of attacks such as adversarial samples and model stealing continue to emerge. Therefore, it is necessary to examine the robustness of the existing privacy protection mechanism under "offensive and defensive thinking", and take the initiative to build a privacy defense system for unknown attacks. At the same time, there is a

certain conflict between privacy protection anti-fraud, and other security goals. How to achieve a balance between privacy and security in the dynamic confrontation is an important topic for future research.

(2) Federated learning privacy protection. Federated learning collaborates to accomplish machine learning tasks in distributed environments through local training and encrypted communication, which opens up new perspectives and paths for privacy protection. Theoretically, it is proved that privacy assurance under a federated framework still faces challenges, and the subsequent research intends to design an efficient privacy mechanism adapted to federated scenarios on the basis of differential privacy, and explore cryptographic tools such as secure multi-party computation and trustworthy execution environments to enhance the system protection capability, to realize the whole-process privacy security from data to model, and from training to inference.

(3) Privacy protection in vertical domains. There are significant differences in the privacy protection needs of different industries and scenarios, and it is often difficult for universal privacy programs to take into account the characteristics of data and task requirements. In the future, we intend to base on vertical industries, fully explore the intrinsic semantics of data, and design targeted privacy protection mechanisms with domain knowledge. For example, in the field of intelligent transportation, focus on the risk of privacy leakage of vehicle track data; in the field of intelligent healthcare, emphasize the privacy protection of sensitive information such as genes and medical records. Promote the formation of privacy protection standards and specifications and security evaluation systems covering key industries to help industrial digital transformation.

(4) Ecological construction of privacy protection. Privacy protection has gone beyond technical issues and requires systematic cross-fertilization of legal, ethical, social, management, and other multidisciplinary perspectives. The subsequent research will explore innovative incentive mechanisms from the perspective of digital economics, consider privacy as a kind of valuable elastic resource, and realize the internal value and external ecology of privacy protection through market-oriented means, to build a credible ecosystem with multi-party participation and benefit sharing. At the same time, privacy protection also calls for the awakening of public privacy awareness, and future research intends to enhance the transparency of blockchain privacy protection using visualization, human-computer interaction, and other technologies, improve user experience, and arouse awareness of the whole society about data privacy protection.

In short, with the deep development of the digital economy, the privacy protection of big data is still a systematic and complex proposition that needs to be tackled urgently, and it is necessary to continue to make efforts in theoretical innovation, technological breakthroughs, standardization, legal norms, industrial policies, and other dimensions. Privacy computing will become the "new infrastructure" in the digital era, which is of great significance to national security, social fairness, and personal dignity. In the future, how to build a new paradigm of privacy protection for international digitalization and complex scenarios, releasing the value of data responsibly and sustainably, and achieving a dynamic balance between data utilization and privacy protection will be a major issue

for academia and the industry. This requires the cooperation of government, industry, academia, and research institutions to build a new ecology of data privacy protection under the multiple regulations of law, technology and ethics.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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